

In the Australian state of Victoria the rate of infection of COVID-19 has increased 126-fold since vaccination started and 1500-fold since vaccination levels rose from low to high: support for Luc Montagnier's claim?

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Abstract

Cases of COVID-19 infection first appeared in many countries early in 2020. For the first year of the subsequent pandemic no vaccines were available. Vaccines began to be employed around February 2021. Under exhortations from most Government Health agencies the rates of vaccination have steadily increased, reaching levels around 90% for first and second doses in many countries. The Nobel prize winning virologist Luc Montagnier warned that vaccination would lead to more transmissible mutations of the virus against which the vaccines were less effective. Data on case numbers and vaccination rates for the Australian state of Victoria have been examined from 26 January 2020 when COVID-19 first appeared to 7 June 2022. Three time periods are distinguished — prevaccination, low levels of vaccination ($< \approx 25\%$ of maximum) and high levels of vaccination. The average rate of infection is 79 times greater when vaccines were employed than in the period preceding vaccination, 126 times greater in the period of high vaccination relative to that in the prevaccination period and 1500 times greater in the period of high vaccination levels relative to that in the period of low vaccination levels. It is certain that vaccination has not reduced the rate of infection and very likely that it has increased it. Furthermore, since vaccination commenced, the transmissibility of new variants has risen sharply to 12 times its value at the beginning of the pandemic. This is supported by calculations of the rates of infection per susceptible which for BA.4/5 are extremely large. These findings lend support to the claim of Luc Montagnier and others about the inadvisability of a massive world-wide vaccination agenda. However, infection rates must eventually drop because increasing case numbers lead to declines in the numbers of susceptibles, already by up to 50% in some countries. However, second and third infections would effectively increase the number of susceptibles.

1 Introduction

The COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2) pandemic has swept across the world for over 2 years since originating presumably in Wuhan, China at the beginning of 2020. Daily case and death numbers are published for 227 countries online [1, 2]. The 50 highest case rates by country are from $\approx 25\%$ to $> 50\%$ and the death rates are from $\approx 0.2\%$ to $\approx 0.6\%$. Many European countries are in the 50 with the highest case rates; the USA is ranked ≈ 50 ; and somewhat surprisingly China, which is considered to be the origin of the pandemic, is ranked 223 of 227 countries with a case rate of $\approx 0.01\%$.

The costs of this SARS-CoV-2 epidemic have been, and continue to be enormous. At time of writing, the number of deaths attributed to the virus is over 6 million, approaching the number of civilian deaths during World War 1. Altogether about a half a billion cases have occurred, causing immense grief to families of victims and placing medical facilities and their staff under enormous strain. Peoples' lives have been shattered by lockdowns and travel restrictions and countless businesses have suffered financial losses and many have been forced to close down. Most schools and Universities have had to abandon live instruction and populations generally have been hampered with time-consuming testing procedures.

2 Variants

Mutations of the COVID-19 virus are commonly called variants which are very numerous [3]. The earliest variant, Wuhan-1, was identified on 24 December 2019 [3], though there have been claims of ancestral strains dating back to October, 2019. The few variants which lead to very significant numbers of infected hosts are called Variants of Concern. Five have been delineated as in Table 1 [3, 4] - but it is noted that notations and dates may vary amongst data sources. In England, for example, the δ variant dominated from April to December 2021, Omicron dominated from December 2021 to February/March 2022 followed by the BA.2 Omicron variant.

Table 1: A summary of Variants of Concern. (* Uncertain)

Common name	Relative Transmissibility	Code name	Date of Origin	Country
Wuhan-1	1	-	12/19	China
β	1.5	B.1.351	5/20	S. Africa
α	1.5	B.1.1.7	9/20	U.K.
δ	2.85	B.167.2	10/20	India
γ	2.6*	B.11.28.1	11/20	Brazil
ξ (Omicron)	5.70	BA.1	11/21	S. Africa
ξ (Omicron)	8.3	BA.2	2/22	S. Africa
ξ (Omicron)	11.6	BA.4/5	1/22, 2/22	S. Africa

Generally, later appearing variants have been more transmissible than the earlier ones. β and α were about 50% more transmissible than the earlier variant and δ was approximately 90% more transmissible than α [5].

For the γ variant which dominated a major outbreak in Brazil from late 2020 and led to more than 142000 deaths, the relative transmissibility is given by various sources as from 1.7 to 2.6, but against unspecified other variants, making the figure

uncertain. However the date of emergence and relative transmissibility of γ is close to that of δ .

Reports concerning the relative transmissibilities of δ and Omicron give widely disparate results though all attribute a much greater value for Omicron. In [6] it was stated that a Danish study had found the R_0 for Omicron was 3.19 larger than that of δ whereas a Japanese study found that Omicron was 4.12 times as transmissible as δ . In another report [7], Omicron was found to lead to about twice as many infected contacts outside the household as δ . Furthermore, in a Euronews report [8], Omicron was found to be 105% more transmissible than δ . Heuristic averaging over these figures gives an increase of infectivity by a factor of between 2 and 3 for Omicron relative to δ .

The Omicron subvariant BA.2 was reported [9] as being 30% to 60% more transmissible than the original BA.1 strain. Following BA.2 the Omicron subvariants BA.4 and BA.5 appeared which are even more transmissible than BA.2 [10]. Table 1 gives estimates of their relative transmissibilities based on the data given in [10] along with those of the other variants. Omicron BA.5 has been described as being as contagious as measles. Although the benefits of vaccination are peddled by many Government and Health Departments there are numerous accounts of its harmful, sometimes fatal, consequences.

Different variants have differing abilities to infect individuals in different age groups, different abilities to evade immune responses, lead to differing amounts of virus in the host (viral load) and may preferentially detrimentally target different organs [6].

3 Vaccines

According to Wikipedia, vaccines against COVID-19 are considered very useful for reducing the spread of the virus and ameliorating its deleterious effects on human health. The two most popular types of vaccine are adenovirus vector vaccines, such as that produced by Oxford-Astrazenica and mRNA vaccines including those of Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna. Up to the end of May 2022, about 12 billion doses of COVID-19 vaccines had been administered throughout the world [11]. Detailed accounts of vaccine types and clinical trials which ascertain their efficacies are given, for example, in [12].

Most Government Health Departments in many countries have emphatically encouraged the public to get vaccinated, with a sequence of 1st dose, 2nd dose, 1st booster and even 2nd booster.

However, some virologists have warned against mass vaccination programs. The first was Luc Montagnier, a Nobel Prize winner for his work on HIV, who in 2021 declared that (a) a mass vaccination program would lead to a procession of variants with increasing ability to infect; and (b) that the COVID-19 virus was the result of laboratory rather than natural procedures [13, 14]. In 2022 Robert Malone, an expert on vaccines who was involved in the production of the first mRNA vaccines, concurred with Luc Montagnier's views [15]. According to Dr Malone, "if the public health regime continues to push this terrible universal vaccination policy, it will keep driving the virus to mutate, potentially to a state where it may be more pathogenic and more able to elude immune response".

In addition to the impact of vaccines in increasing the number and strength of variants, the vaccines themselves may have numerous unwanted harmful effects such as myocarditis, thrombosis, thrombocytopenia, vasculitis, cardiac, Bells Palsy and cardiac arrest [16, 17]. Documents released by the Food and Drug Admin-

istration (FDA) reveal that Pfizer found nearly 160,000 adverse reactions to its COVID-19 vaccine in the early stages of its rollout, including 1223 which were fatal, more than 25000 nervous system disorders, 17000 musculoskeletal and connective tissue disorders, 14000 gastrointestinal disorders, 270 miscarriages, as well as cases of epilepsy, heart failure and stroke [18]. Furthermore, evidence has been reported recently that the Pfizer mRNA vaccine may lead to modification of host DNA [19].

When the Omicron variant appeared, a concern of many scientists was that it could bypass vaccine efficacy and immunization, because of the large number of mutations in Omicron relative to earlier variants. Furthermore, according to Dr Malone, Omicron is not only resistant to the vaccines, but the infectivity of more recent variants may be facilitated by the vaccine. It is disturbing that in January 2022 a Public Health Scotland COVID-19 and Winter Statistical Report stated that in the previous 4 weeks double and triple vaccinated individuals had higher case rates than unvaccinated individuals. Equally problematic was a December 2021 report from the Canadian Covid Care Alliance, which is composed of independent health care professionals, claiming that Pfizer's vaccine could cause more harm than good.

4 COVID-19 case data for the state of Victoria

A detailed study of COVID-19 case and vaccination data for the 2nd most populous Australian state of Victoria from [20] is used to examine the relationship between case rate and vaccination coverage. Figure 1 shows the data for the early part of the epidemic. The left hand panel is for the first 13 months of the outbreak from January 2020 to February 2021. During this period no vaccines were administered as none were available. In the upper record daily case data is plotted against time whereas in the lower record the moving average over 7 day windows of the daily case numbers is shown.

There are two well defined peaks. A smaller one of duration about 47 days with a daily maximum of about 100 cases beginning and ending at 29 March and 23 April respectively; and a larger one of duration about 110 days with a daily maximum of about 700 cases from 14 June to 2 October. According to the data of Table 1 on the dates of first appearances of variants the first of these peaks is most likely due to the Wuhan-1 variant and the second peak is most likely due mainly to the β variant.

The results plotted in the right hand panel of Figure 1 are for 22 February 2021 to 19 August 2021 which is the time period immediately after vaccination commenced. The top graph (blue) is for daily case numbers, the middle one is for the moving average of case numbers (black) and the bottom graph is of the total number of vaccinations administered. The case numbers do start to increase towards the end of this period as do vaccination numbers which reach about 4 million.

For days 393 to 484 (22 February to 24 May) there are less than 10 cases per day; for days 484 to 536 (24 May to 15 July) there are less than or equal to 10 cases per day; there is then a minor outbreak with a peak of 28 cases at day 544 (23 July). At day 556 (4 August) there are 25 cases which is the start of the sustained outbreak seen in the left panel of Figure 2.

The left panel of Figure 2 shows that during the 3 month period from 19 August 2021 to 17 November 2021, daily case numbers rose slowly to reach a maximum of 2243 on around October 16 (day 629) and then declined less slowly to about 838

Figure 1: **Left panel.** Plots of daily case numbers (blue curve) for COVID-19 infection and moving average (black curve) in Victoria during the period immediately prior to the commencement of vaccination, 26 January 2020 to 21 February 2021. **Right panel.** The top two graphs are the daily case numbers (blue curve) and their moving average (black curve) for the period 22 February 2021 to 19 August 2021. In the lowermost graph the cumulative number of vaccination doses administered is plotted against days from the beginning of the epidemic (blue curve).

on day 660 (16 November). This outbreak was thus considerably larger than the two previous outbreaks. Total vaccinations rose from 4.03 million to 10.4 million during this period.

Figure 2: **Left panel.** The top two graphs are the daily case numbers (blue curve) and their moving average (black curve) for the period 19 August 2021 to 17 November 2021. In the lowermost graph the cumulative number of vaccination doses administered is plotted against days from the beginning of the epidemic (blue curve). **Right panel.** As in the left panel but for 17 November to 22 December 2021.

In the right hand panel of Figure 2 it is seen that in the month from 17 November to 22 December 2021 the daily case numbers were fairly constant with

a maximum of 1611 around 18 December 2021. The moving average has a steady upward trend. Start and finish values were 838 and 1289 daily cases, respectively. Total vaccinations rose from 10.4 million to 11.0 million during this period.

Results for the last two epochs before 7 June 2022 are shown in Figure 3. The left panel shows results for the first of these epochs, from 22 December 2021 to 4 February 2022 which contains the largest outbreak since cases were first observed. The beginning and end of this epoch are at 695 and 740 days respectively after the first cases in late January 2020. The number of daily cases, as seen in the top graph (blue curve), starts at 1289 and has exceeded the levels of all previous outbreaks within a week, climbing to 5100 at day 705 and then rising dramatically to a maximum of 46995 by day 714. Thereafter a steady decline occurs to a still very large number of 12398 cases at the end of this epoch. The moving average of cases shown in the middle graph (black curve) exhibits a broad maximum, the approach to which is faster than the decline. During this epoch the total number of vaccinations, plotted in the bottom graph (blue curve) rose from 11.0 million to 13.3 million.

Figure 3: **Left panel.** Uppermost plot, daily case numbers (blue curve) for COVID-19 infection during the period 22 December 2021 to 4 February 2022 (days 695 to 740). Middle plot, 7-day moving average (black curve). Bottom plot, total vaccine doses **Right panel.** As in the left panel but for the period 3 February to June 7 2022.

The right hand panel of Figure 3 shows results for a recent, (at time of writing) period, being from 3 March 2022 to 7 June 2022 or days 740 to 864 after the first appearance of the virus.

The maximum number of daily cases (top graph, blue curve) is 14200 at day 838 and the minimum is 2939 at day 863, one day before the last day of the epoch which has 9181 cases. The moving average (middle graph, black curve) starts at 10865 and has broad fluctuations within the range 6123 and 12465 with a value of 6506 at the end of the epoch. During this epoch the total number of vaccinations (bottom graph, blue curve) rose from 13.3 million to 15.5 million.

Figure 4 contains the results of case numbers and their moving average in the most recent time period from 8 June to 13 July 2022 during which vaccinations, counting all doses and boosters, increased from 15.6 million to 15.9 million. The mean of the daily case numbers for this period is 7595 and the moving average has a small positive trend.

Figure 4: Daily case numbers (blue curve) and their 7-day moving average (black curve) for COVID-19 infection during the period of 36 days from 8 June to 13 July 2022. In the lower panel the linear line of best fit is shown in red.

4.1 Overall picture

Figure 5 shows the time courses from 26 January 2020 to June 7 2022 of the following three quantities: total cases (black curve), moving average (blue curve) and total vaccinations administered (red curve). The vertical scale is only applicable to the moving average which has a maximum of about 40000. The curves for total cases and total vaccinations have been normalized by scaling them to pass through the upper right extreme point at [864, 45000]. The actual values were 1951581 cases and 15459404 vaccinations as at day 864 (7 June 2022).

On the curve for the total vaccinations is marked the value v_c which was considered a critical value because this occurred on day 570 which signalled the major outbreak rising from 25 cases on 19 August 2021 to 2243 on 16 October 2021. The value of v_c corresponds to 25% of the maximum of the total vaccinations whose unnormalized value is 3864851.

Inspection of the curves in Figure 5 reveals that case daily numbers of COVID-19 remained comparatively low at always ≤ 700 before day 570 when vaccination numbers were low. The graph of moving average has 6 local maxima as in the following Table.

Table 2: Properties of local maxima of moving average

No.	Day	Dates	Magnitude	Vaccine doses
1	65	30 March 2020	74	0
2	190	3 August 2020	533	0
3	631	17 October 2021	1932	8707919
4	717	9 January 2022	38400	11688410
5	801	3 April 2022	10300	14778188
6	841	13 May 2022	12600	15194160

There are two maxima in the prevaccination period and four after vaccination commenced. It is natural to ask what variants might be dominating these maxima.

If it is assumed that the outbreaks in Victoria were started by infected arrivals from overseas with delays due to travel, then it does not seem possible to relate the dates of the Victorian outbreaks to the dates of origin of various variants of concern in Table 1. A possible explanation is that the outbreaks in Victoria were the result of mutations in virus present in infected individuals in Victoria or other Australian states. Since Victoria and other Australian states have had vaccination rates amongst the highest in the world, then by Montagnier’s hypothesis it is quite plausible that variants of concern found in Australia were of local origin and not from overseas.

Figure 5: The blue curve is the 7-day moving average of COVID-19 cases from 26 January 2020 to 7 June 2022; the black curve is the total number of cases normalized to pass through [864, 45000]; and the red curve is the total number of vaccinations, also normalized. Also depicted is the value v_c of total vaccinations at which the number of cases starts to increase substantially.

5 Astounding statistics

We consider the period of 864 days from first appearance of the virus to 7 June 2022, during which vaccination took place at rates reaching about 90% for first and second doses.

Table 3: A comparison of infection rates during 3 stages of vaccination

Time period	Duration	Vax cover	V	Cases	Cases/day
26/1/20-21/2/21	393 d	None	$V = 0$	20478	52.1
22/2/21-19/8/21	179 d	Low	$0 < V \leq V_C$	792	4.4
20/8/21-7/6/22	292 d	High	$V > V_C$	1930311	6610.7

Let $V(d), d = 1 \dots 864$ be the number of vaccine doses up to day d which has values in $[0, V_{max}]$ where $V_{max} = 1951581$ which occurs on day 864. In Table 3 the amounts and rates of infection by COVID-19 in the state of Victoria are given for the following three regimes.

- Zero vaccination ($V = 0$) from day 1 to day 393.
- Low vaccination rate $0 < V \leq V_C$ from day 394 to day 572, where V_C is 26.9% of V_{max} .
- High vaccination rate with $V > V_C$ from day 573 to day 864.

During the pre-vaccination period of 393 days there were 20478 cases with an average per day rate of 52.1. In the subsequent period of 179 days with vaccination $0 < V \leq V_C$ there were 792 cases with a per day rate 4.4. During the period of high vaccination rates $V > V_C$ there were the enormous number 1930311 of cases with an average per day rate of 6610.7.

Thus the rate of infection in the high vaccination rate regime is 126 times that in the prevaccination period and, incredibly, 1500 times greater than that in the low vaccination rate period. These results are further illustrated in Figure 6 where cases $C(d)$ to day d divided by time d elapsed, are plotted against d with the three vaccination regimes indicated.

Figure 6: A plot of $C(d)/d$ versus d for the Victorian COVID-19 epidemic where $1 \leq d \leq 864$ (26 January 2020 to 7 June 2022). The three regimes indicated are zero vaccination and low and high vaccination coverage.

6 Discussion

The efficacy E of a vaccine is defined as

$$E = \frac{R_U - R_V}{R_U} \quad (1)$$

where R_U is the rate of infection in an unvaccinated population and R_V is the the rate of infection in a vaccinated population. One could interpret E as the

probability that a vaccinated uninfected individual is infected on contact with an infected individual.

The U.S. Food and Drug Administration recommends vaccines tested in clinical trials against COVID-19 have an efficacy of at least 50% [21]. According to early data the efficacies of commonly employed vaccines are AstraZeneca, 70%, Pfizer, 95% and Moderna, 95% [22]. Efficacy however depends on the variant and various biological properties of the host.

Simulation studies of a stochastic epidemic model of SIR type which approximates the evolution of a COVID-19 outbreak [23] have shown that case numbers depend approximately linearly on the probability of transmission and approximately linearly on the number of susceptibles. If a vaccine is efficacious then it should reduce the probability of transmission of the virus from infected to uninfected individuals and/or prevent the replication of the virus after transmission. Hence with an efficacious vaccine, even one with an efficacy of less than 100%, as the percentage of a population which is vaccinated increases, the daily case numbers should decrease. This has not been the case for the vaccines for COVID-19 whose administration has seen a dramatic increase in case numbers when vaccination coverage was at its highest.

Figure 7: Showing the increase in transmissibility relative to the original Wuhan variant of COVID-19 variants with order of appearance.

Another alarming feature concerns the time course of the relative transmissibilities of variants. During the pre-vaccination period up to February 2021 there were 5 main variants, Wuhan-1, β , α , δ and γ with an average relative transmissibility of 1.89. Since vaccination commenced, the variants which have emerged have had relative transmissibilities of 3.01 (BA.1), 4.4 (BA.2) and 6.1 (BA.4/5) times greater than the average before vaccination. This is illustrated in Figure 7 where a bar graph shows relative transmissibilities of variants plotted against order of appearance. The time course of the growth looks exponential-like.

6.1 Rates per susceptible

The increasing transmissibility of the sequence of Omicron variants can be made evident by plotting the daily rate of infections per susceptible rather than just

plotting daily cases. To do this we make two assumptions. Firstly that for the state of Victoria, the initial number S_{tot} of susceptibles is about a half of the population; that is 3 million. The second assumption is that an individual who has been infected with COVID-19 is no longer susceptible. This latter assumption is an approximation because it is known that individuals who have recovered can be re-infected. Thus we have for this rough calculation that the number of susceptibles S at day d is

$$S(d) = S_{tot} - C(d), \quad (2)$$

where C was defined earlier. The daily rate of infection per susceptible is then simply

$$R_S(d) = c(d)/S(d), \quad (3)$$

where $c(d)$ is the number of new cases on day d . Both daily rates of infection per person and per susceptible are plotted in Figure 8. The upper panel shows the rates and the lower panel shows their moving averages. The first peak at about day 714 in each record corresponds to the early Omicron variants. This is followed by three local minima at days 765, 810 and 865, with local maxima at days 801, 843 and 906, the latter being the last day shown. Rates per susceptible give a better idea of the transmissibility of the subsequent Omicron variants. The rapid rate of increase of the last part of the graph suggests that indeed, as alluded to above, the BA.4/5 variants are more transmissible than the earlier Omicron variants.

Figure 8: The top panel shows the daily case numbers per person (blue curve) and per susceptible (red curve). Corresponding moving averages are shown in the lower panel.

6.2 Concluding remarks

In light of the facts presented above, it is natural to ask, “What are the benefits and drawbacks of vaccination?” In the light of much support for vaccination by

Table 4: Advantages and disadvantages of massive vaccination program

Advantages	Disadvantages
Can prevent infection	Increased rate of appearance of new variants
Can reduce the severity of symptoms	Increased transmissibility of variants
Can reduce the chance of a fatal attack	Can cause dangerous side effects including death May alter host DNA

so many health and industry authorities, it would surely not be possible to claim that COVID-19 vaccines are in themselves not useful. However there could be a trade-off between the benefit of vaccination in preventing transmission of the virus and in reducing the severity of symptoms and the strong possibility that the greater the vaccination rate the more likely it is that there is an increased rate of appearance of new variants and that some new variants will have greater ability to infect unvaccinated and even some vaccinated individuals.

What would have been the consequence of not employing vaccines at all? According to the data for Victoria it is likely that there would have been spasmodic sparse outbreaks unless a more infectious variant arrived from overseas. This latter possibility confuses the issue as to whether high vaccination rates are to blame for the very large outbreaks which have occurred from October 2021 to July 2022. Thus although the claims of Luc Montagnier and Robert Malone about the hazards of a massive vaccination program seem to be correct, there is the possibility that refraining from such a program would have not completely avoided recent severe outbreaks. However it is likely that not embarking on such a program of vaccination would have led to outbreaks of reduced size and duration.

Finally, we note that some virologists have presented strong evidence that this particular corona virus, COVID-19, was developed by China as a bioweapon [24]. This has been disputed by China and several internationally acclaimed public health organizations. Notwithstanding the veracity or otherwise of such claims there is no doubt that COVID-19 is inflicting heavy health, economic and societal damage on the majority of countries particularly the United States and its allies but that China itself is practically unaffected with negligible infection rates and brutal lockdowns on its population when a minor outbreak occurs.

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